

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MASSAQUOI****FIRST NAME: JAMES CONRAD****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MSS Word, Office 365 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The structure and process of writing an academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-13)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Language variants –American vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1)INTRODUCTION

That time I have ever dreamed of is finally here. I am finally taking that bold step to tread the path through another academic journey, studying for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in International Public Health (DIPH) at Euclid University. I cannot overstate my degree of excitement, driven by my passion and dedication, to pursue this program. It is interesting to note that this follows a failed attempt with Walden University, where I enrolled for a Doctor of Public Health (DrPH) but unfortunately discontinued due to the unaffordability of fees to cover the duration of the course.

ACA-401/ACA-401D has provided a raft of guides and, in some instances, rules of thumb to academic writing. This paper, which is my first in this program, is on writing a good academic essay. It provides a detailed review of the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D to produce a succinct outline of my understanding of the course pack, which aims to provide a guide to students at Euclid University on academic essay writing. I have taken time to review the well-structured, simple, and easily comprehensible seventy-two-page document that also provides a guide to structure, links to clear guidelines, and recommended references for academic writing. While this guide is intended for students at Euclid University, its depth and ease of reference also make it a valuable resource for

students from other academic institutions. The following paragraphs highlight my review of the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D.

2) WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

In writing an academic essay, it is always useful to determine the type of essay you want. The academic essay must be nonfictional writing produced as part of your academic work and follow a coherent format with citations and references to the works of others. The essay must also reflect a critical analysis and contribution to the scope of the topic or subject matter (EUCLID 2021, 7). A well-researched, critically analyzed, and properly structured academic paper easily finds its way into journals, books, and reputable publications. EUCLID (2021, 7) has provided a three-step approach to writing an academic essay. The ladder pyramid involves steps from analysis of the question and definitions of terms, moving further up the ladder to researching the topic using credible academic sources, writing your paper, and getting it peer-reviewed by a colleague before submission. I have also personally found these steps useful in preparing this submission which I have diligently followed, only excepting the peer review.

As often stressed and as would be discussed under the topic "plagiarism" below, it is a MUST that any academic paper or essay is properly referenced. This requires an understanding of the referencing style of the facility, school, or journal (EUCLID 2021, 11). Therefore, it is prudent to consult other credible sources, read and digest what is posited in those sources, and critically analyze before composing your essay, diligently giving credit to those sources as the case may be.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

When used in academic essays, punctuation must be as accurate as possible to avoid misunderstanding the facts presented in the essay (Snooks and Co. 2002, 7). Therefore, it is advisable to use punctuation as sparingly as would be necessary to retain the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16). The review of this course pack reminds me of some common mistakes in the placement of punctuation marks. Some examples, such as an apostrophe in 'it's' with its variant 'its,' without an apostrophe, as is the case with the placement of bullets, commas, colons, semi-colons, and other punctuations. The phrase 'Monkeys host ebola virus' without a comma, for example, carries a different meaning from its variant 'Monkeys, host ebola virus'. (EUCLID 2021, 19).

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Academic writings have not been without errors coming with inconsistency between American and British English due to the dominant influence of American English over British English. These two variants of the English language can be confusing, especially to non-native American or British English speakers or scholars. The confusion

is more prominent with different pronunciations but with the same spellings, different spellings but same pronunciations, different but similar spellings and pronunciations, same words but different meanings or grammar, syntax, and punctuations in general usage. (EUCLID 2021, 25-32). In my writing, I have used the language proofing icon to set their language preference as directed in the course pack ACA-404/ACA-401D. It is also explicit on the use of the two variants of English, which could be a silver bullet for good academic writing.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is considered a serious academic fraud that could lead to serious consequences. Merriam-Webster online dictionary, 2017 has defined plagiarism as "the act of stealing or using another person's words or ideas without crediting the source" (Turnitin, LLC, 2017). I also find it ethically wrong to use someone else's work or knowledge without giving credit to their work. The seriousness attached to issues of plagiarism makes it increasingly important to avoid such academic offense by simply citing sources or giving credit to authors of materials used in your work which must be indicated as in-text citations and included in the works cited (EUCLID 2021, 34). Such sources, if directly quoted, may be placed in quotation marks, and where a quote is more than four lines, the quote should be indented as a separate paragraph (EUCLID 2021, 35).

While the importance of citing to prevent plagiarism is stressed in the preceding paragraphs, it is also important to note that not everything must be cited. EUCLID (2021, 37) has provided examples of such, some of which are of common knowledge and that cannot be cited. The guide also provides guidance on specific formats for referencing (EUCLID 2021, 38-39).

6) STYLE GUIDES IN ACADEMIC WRITING

Academic writing calls for consistency with style guides making it important to keep abreast with guidelines as they are published. The published guidelines ensure that authors do not necessarily adopt a personal writing style but rather fall in line with the publication, company, or website hosting the writing. To a large extent, some creative writers who believe in their ability to follow standard writing styles tend to avoid the use of style guides. However, this approach has not already proven to be the case since it argues that style guides allow for consistency in the writers writing output (EUCLID 2021, 41). EUCLID 2021 has defined a style guide as a "means of documentation of your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent". These guides are generally used for specific writing, including technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2021, 41).

I have realized that styles in academic writing may not only provide guides on punctuation or grammar but also provides a guide on preferred lengths of sentences, manuscript layout, font usage, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, and structure,

among others. This aspect only further stresses the importance of a style guide as an invaluable tool for any writer, whether a freelance writer or an academic writer (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). EUCLID (2021, 42) has provided some useful references such as Shrunck's 'the element of style,' the Economist Style Guide, the Chicago Manual of Style, and the BBC News Style for settling styles, much of which I have found quite enriching.

7) CONCLUSION

I have found the course pack ACA-401D very enriching and informative. Doctoral students at Euclid University need to master the art of academic writing by following standard rules, structures, and formats. Additionally, the course pack has also provided guides to abbreviations, acronyms and initialisms, and capitalizations, and also introduced (with details) the Chicago manual of style (CMS) or the Turabian manual, which are all important elements of academic writing. ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack is a valuable resource that will guide my doctoral journey.

REFERENCES

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